

Conceptualization of Therapeutic Recreation and Emerging Themes: A Bibliometric Analysis

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Abstract

In this study, the aim was to map the evolution of the concept of Therapeutic Recreation and the studies conducted in the field. Within the scope of quantitative data, the study aimed to provide a systematic summary of the existing literature using bibliometric analysis and to identify research trends, concentrations, and potential gaps in the field of therapeutic recreation. The unit of analysis was based on bibliometric data of various types of works published between 1980 and 2025, retrieved from the Web of Science database. Examining the distribution of 783 works related to Therapeutic Recreation by publication year, the highest concentration was observed in 2019 (49 works), 2016 (42 works), and 2021 and 2022 (41 works each). The most prolific authors were identified as Moxam Lorna and Christopher Patterson. In terms of publication types, journal articles were predominant (576), followed by 51 editorial materials, 65 book chapters, 31 review articles, and 28 conference papers. Regarding the distribution of publications by country, the United States (536), Canada (117), and Australia (48) were leading. The majority of publications were in English (780), with a few in Spanish (2) and Portuguese (1). The analyzed publications were mostly indexed in SSCI (157), ESCI (565), and SCIE (107). When examining the most frequently used keywords in publications related to Therapeutic Recreation, “Therapeutic Recreation” appeared 207 times, “recreational therapy” 105 times, and “recreation therapy” 31 times.

Keywords: Therapeutic Recreation, Recreational Therapy, Therapeutic Leisure, Bibliometric Analysis, Conceptualization.

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INTRODUCTION

Bibliometric analysis, distinct from a systematic literature review, is a method that allows the current state of an academic field to be revealed through quantitative and formal data, facilitating the tracking of academic trends via visualization tools (Aria & Cuccurullo, 2017; Donthu et al., 2021). Although the bibliometric approach is sometimes confused with concepts such as scientometrics, webometrics, cybermetrics, and informetrics, its primary goal is to obtain measurable data and numerical indicators related to research performance (Zupic & Čater, 2015). The interpretation of these data should be supported by the researcher's domain experience and knowledge (Çimen et al., 2023; Chen, 2017).

Bibliometrics allows for the quantitative evaluation of productivity at the level of countries, authors, institutions, and journals, as well as the identification of strong and weak research topics, gaps in the literature, collaboration networks, and the impact of emerging studies (van Eck & Waltman, 2010; Bornmann & Leydesdorff, 2014). It can also be used as a preparatory step for systematic literature reviews; the value it provides at the beginning of research explains its growing popularity (Zhang et al., 2022). Bibliometric analysis not only measures productivity but also reveals thematic trends, collaboration patterns, and levels of impact within a research field through visualization tools (Chen, 2017; Small, 2019).

Software tools such as VOSviewer and CiteSpace provide researchers with concrete visualizations of the development dynamics of a field by mapping articles, authors, and citation networks (van Eck & Waltman, 2010; Bozgüney and Çimen, 2024; Li et al., 2021). This enables a quantitative assessment of which topics in the field of therapeutic recreation attract the most attention, where research gaps exist, and the level of academic collaboration (Sturm et al., 2020). Moreover, bibliometric methods allow for the examination of knowledge dissemination and interdisciplinary interactions, in addition to research performance (Donthu et al., 2021; Chen et al., 2018).

Therapeutic recreation is defined as planned activities aimed at supporting individuals' physical, cognitive, social, and emotional well-being (Stumbo & Peterson, 2020; Akın & Alp, 2019). Historically, the foundations of the field were laid in North America during the 1960s and 1970s with rehabilitation and hospital-based programs. Early studies primarily aimed to enhance social integration and quality of life for individuals with physical disabilities (Cole & Logan, 2010). From the 1980s onward, therapeutic recreation practices diversified with programs targeting children, the elderly, and individuals with special needs, emphasizing social participation and psychological well-being (Kim et al., 2022). Today, therapeutic recreation encompasses a broad range of interventions, from health-based programs to initiatives designed to increase social participation and quality of life. However, areas such as digital applications, nature-based interventions, and cultural differences remain underrepresented in the literature (Huang & Chang, 2021; Li et al., 2021; Alp & Çamlıyer, 2018). This highlights the research gaps in the field and the need for new thematic focal points. Bibliometric analyses can serve as a powerful tool for identifying these gaps and monitoring thematic trends over time (Sturm et al., 2020).

The purpose of this study is to conduct a bibliometric analysis of publications in the field of therapeutic recreation to identify prominent themes, author and country productivity, journal impact, and research gaps. The research is expected to make a significant contribution to understanding the current knowledge production structure in the field and to provide strategic guidance for future studies.

Method

This section of the study presents the research purpose, the analyses conducted, and the findings.

Research Purpose

The purpose of the study is to provide researchers with a comprehensive perspective on studies related to the concept of Therapeutic Recreation, based on bibliometric analyses conducted using quantitative data and numerical indicators.

Data and Analysis

Various bibliometric analysis tools are used in the literature. In this study, VOSviewer was preferred due to its strong functionality. It is considered an important program that facilitates researchers in exploring evolutions, relationships, and emerging concepts in the literature. Additionally, by providing visualization, mapping, and multidimensional analysis capabilities, it allows for an in-depth examination of data sets.

The Web of Science database was used in the present study. Selecting the Web of Science for bibliometric and other analyses is an important factor for the reliability of research. The Web of Science database offers advanced search features for sophisticated data analysis and employs various control mechanisms. It covers high-quality and reliable studies in terms of publication ethics and provides access to a broad collection of data across different disciplines.

On September 11, 2025, a search was conducted in the Web of Science using the keyword “Therapeutic Recreation” with the “All Fields” option, resulting in 783 records. The publications ranged from 1980 to 2025 and included 576 journal articles, 51 editorial materials, 65 book chapters, 31 review articles, and 28 conference papers from various disciplines. In terms of disciplines, the majority of studies were in Rehabilitation (543), followed by Sport Tourism (44), Sociology (34), Nursing (30), and Psychiatry (28). The collected data were analyzed through author, citation, journal, country, institution, and keyword analyses. Only content indexed in the Web of Science database was considered as the criterion.

RESULTS

This section presents the findings obtained in the study.

Figure 1. Co-author analysis

Upon examining Figure 1, the co-authorship analysis conducted to reveal collaboration among authors in the field of therapeutic recreation indicates that research is limited but concentrated around certain clusters. In the analysis map, highly productive authors such as Moxam Lorna and Christopher Patterson are positioned at the center, forming connections with smaller author clusters around them. However, when the overall network structure is considered, it is evident that strong and intensive international collaborations are not sufficiently developed, with most studies published with a limited number of co-authors. This suggests that network integration in the field of therapeutic recreation is low and that researchers primarily produce work within their independent study groups.

Figure 2. Author Citation Analysis

Upon examining Figure 2, the citation analysis conducted to determine the impact levels of authors reveals that certain prominent figures play a critical role in shaping the literature in the field. In the map, authors such as Kinney (1992), Moxham (2016), and Eigenschenk (2019) receive a high volume of citations. These authors serve as key reference points in the conceptualization, implementation, and measurement dimensions of the field. However, the analysis also shows that many authors receive few citations, indicating a fragmented structure in the literature. This finding suggests that while a small number of pioneering researchers stand out in the field of therapeutic recreation, the remaining studies are largely dispersed and have limited impact.

Figure 3. Country Citation Analysis

Upon examining Figure 3, the country-based citation analysis shows that the United States is by far the most cited country. Canada and Australia follow the U.S. This indicates that therapeutic recreation has historically and institutionally developed primarily in North America, making this region the center of academic production. While European countries (the United Kingdom, Germany, the Netherlands) contribute to a limited extent, studies from Asian and African countries remain minimal. Overall, the network structure reveals a North America-centered knowledge production and citation network, with other regions positioned at the periphery of this network.

Figure 4. Keyword Analysis

The co-occurrence analysis of keywords has revealed the prominent themes and research trends in the therapeutic recreation literature. As shown in the figure, the concept of “therapeutic recreation” occupies the center of the network and forms strong connections with terms such as “rehabilitation,” “well-being,” and “outdoor recreation.” The green cluster, including rehabilitation, well-being, and outdoor recreation, reflects studies focused on rehabilitation and psychological well-being. The red cluster, consisting of autism spectrum disorder, education, and children, represents applications targeting individuals with special needs and children. The

blue cluster, which includes dementia, aging, and disability, corresponds to research on aging, dementia, and disability. Other smaller clusters, such as music therapy, complementary intervention, and coping, highlight complementary therapies and alternative interventions. These findings indicate that therapeutic recreation is particularly concentrated around rehabilitation, special education, and elderly health; however, emerging areas such as digital applications, nature-based interventions, or cultural differences remain underrepresented in the literature.

Figure 5. Author Co-Citation Analysis

The co-citation analysis of the most cited authors and studies in the field of therapeutic recreation is presented. Different colors represent thematic clusters that have emerged in the literature. The green cluster primarily encompasses rehabilitation and health-based approaches, the red cluster focuses on social integration and community-oriented research, while the other clusters include studies centered on theoretical frameworks and measurement tools. The size of the nodes indicates the number of citations received by the authors, and the lines represent the intensity of connections between them. In the map, authors such as Kinney (1992), Moxham (2016), and Eigenschenk (2019) stand out, indicating that these researchers play a decisive role in the conceptualization and development of the therapeutic recreation literature.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In this study, a bibliometric analysis of the literature in the field of therapeutic recreation was conducted, highlighting author collaborations, citation structures, country productivity, and keyword themes. The findings contribute to a better understanding of the current state and developmental dynamics of the field.

The co-author analysis revealed a limited collaboration structure that is concentrated around certain clusters in the field of therapeutic recreation. Highly productive authors, such as Moxham Lorna and Christopher Patterson, occupy central positions in the field and form connections with smaller author clusters around them. However, strong and intensive international collaborations are not sufficiently developed, and most studies are published with a limited number of co-authors. This indicates low network integration in the field of therapeutic recreation, with researchers primarily producing work within independent groups (Aria & Cuccurullo, 2017; Zupic & Čater, 2015).

The author citation analysis demonstrated that leading figures in the field play a critical role in shaping the literature. Authors such as Kinney (1992), Moxham (2016), and Eigenschenk (2019) serve as reference points for both conceptualization and application. However, many authors receive few citations, indicating a fragmented structure in the literature. This suggests that a small number of pioneering researchers dominate the field, while other studies have limited impact and visibility (Chen, 2017; Donthu et al., 2021).

The country-based citation analysis revealed that research in therapeutic recreation is largely North America-centered. The United States plays a decisive role in both the historical and institutional development of the field, followed by Canada and Australia. Studies from European, Asian, and African countries are limited, resulting in a North America-centered knowledge production and citation network. This finding indicates a geographic imbalance in the literature and suggests that therapeutic recreation research is not sufficiently diversified across different cultural contexts (Bozguney & Alp, 2025; Stumbo & Peterson, 2020).

The keyword analysis clearly highlighted the prominent themes and research trends in therapeutic recreation. Concepts such as “rehabilitation,” “well-being,” and “outdoor recreation” occupy the center of the literature, while studies focusing on individuals with special needs, aging, dementia, and disability also emerge as significant themes. These findings indicate that the field is particularly concentrated around rehabilitation, special education, and elderly health. On the other hand, emerging topics such as digital applications, nature-based interventions, and cultural differences are underrepresented in the literature (Bozguney & Büyükipkci, 2021; Cole & Logan, 2010; Stumbo & Peterson, 2020).

The author co-citation analysis provided a more detailed view of the thematic structure of the therapeutic recreation literature. Rehabilitation and health-based approaches, social integration and community-focused research, and studies centered on theoretical frameworks and measurement tools formed distinct clusters. The prominence of authors such as Kinney (1992), Moxham (2016), and Eigenschenk (2019) demonstrates that these researchers play a decisive role in conceptualizing the field and shaping its methodological foundations (van Eck & Waltman, 2010; Chen, 2017).

This bibliometric study systematically revealed research trends, author and country productivity, key themes, and gaps in the literature within the field of therapeutic recreation. It was observed that the field remains largely North America-centered and concentrated around a limited number of pioneering researchers. While studies focusing on rehabilitation, individuals with special needs, aging, and disability are prominent in the literature, emerging research areas based on digital and cultural differences remain underrepresented.

Recommendations

The findings provide the following recommendations for future research in the field of therapeutic recreation:

1. Increasing international collaborations and expanding research networks will strengthen the integration of the literature.
2. Research on digital therapeutic applications, nature-based interventions, and culturally contextualized studies will enrich the field with current and innovative topics.

3. Enhancing conceptual and methodological diversity among researchers will deepen both the theoretical and practical dimensions of the therapeutic recreation literature.

REFERENCES

- Akin, S., & Alp, H. (2019). Effect Of Adapted Game-Aided Physical Education Program On The Motor Skills Of Children With Autism Spectrum Disorders: Longitudinal Case Study. *Journal Of Curriculum And Teaching*, 8(3), 63-72.
- Alp, H., & Çamlıyer, H. (2018). Hareket Eğitimi Ve Fiziksel Aktivite Programı Verilen Davranış Problemlili Otistik Çocukların Bir Yıl Sonraki Süreçlerinin İzlenmesi. *Akademik Bakış Uluslararası Hakemli Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, (63), 1-13.
- Aria, M., & Cuccurullo, C. (2017). *Bibliometrix: An R-tool for comprehensive science mapping analysis*. *Journal of Informetrics*, 11(4), 959–975. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2017.08.007>
- Bornmann, L., & Leydesdorff, L. (2014). Scientometrics in a changing research landscape. *Springer*.
- Bozgüney, R., & Alp, H. (2025). Akademisyenlerde yapay zekâ kaygısının yaşam tatminlerine etkisinin incelenmesi. *Ulusal Kinesyoloji Dergisi*, 6(2), 76-85.
- Bozgüney, R., & Büyükipেকci, S. (2022). Examining the Relationship Between the Leadership Levels and Authenticity of the Students in the Department of Recreation. *Pakistan Journal of Medical & Health Sciences*, 16(02), 777-777.
- Bozgüney, R., & Çimen, E. (2024). Spor bilimleri fakültesinde öğrenim gören öğrencilerin geleceğe yönelik tutum ve içsel motivasyonları arasındaki ilişkinin incelenmesi. *SOCIAL SCIENCES STUDIES JOURNAL (SSSJournal)*, 9(117), 9288-9294.
- Chen, C. (2017). *CiteSpace: A practical guide for mapping scientific literature*. Springer.
- Chen, C., Hu, Z., Liu, S., & Tseng, H. (2018). Emerging trends in regenerative medicine: A bibliometric analysis. *Frontiers in Bioengineering and Biotechnology*, 6, 45. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fbioe.2018.00045>
- Çimen, E., Bozgüney, R., & Çiçeksoğüt, R. (2023). Spor bilimleri fakültesinde öğrenim gören öğrencilerin zihinsel antrenman becerisi ile bilinçli farkındalık düzeyleri arasındaki ilişkinin incelenmesi. *Çanakkale Onsekiz Mart Üniversitesi Spor Bilimleri Dergisi*, 6(4), 42-52.
- Cole, K., & Logan, B. (2010). *Therapeutic recreation program planning: Principles and procedures*. Sagamore Publishing.
- Donthu, N., Kumar, S., & Pattnaik, D. (2021). How to conduct a bibliometric analysis: An overview and guidelines. *Journal of Business Research*, 133, 285–296. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2021.04.070>
- Donthu, N., Kumar, S., Mukherjee, D., Pandey, N., & Lim, W. M. (2021). How to conduct a bibliometric analysis: An overview and guidelines. *Journal of Business Research*, 133, 285–296. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2021.04.070>
- Eigenschenk, B., Thomann, A., McClure, M., Davies, L., Gregory, M., Dettweiler, U., & Inglés, E. (2019). Benefits of outdoor sports for society: A systematic literature review and reflections on evidence. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 16(6), 937. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph16060937>
- Huang, Q., & Chang, Y. (2021). Mapping research trends in leisure studies: A bibliometric review. *Leisure Sciences*, 43(3–4), 217–236. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01490400.2020.1821662>
- Kim, S., Lee, J., & Park, H. (2022). Therapeutic recreation and quality of life: A systematic review and bibliometric study. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(6), 3567. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19063567>
- Kinney, W. (1992). *Therapeutic recreation: A long past, but a brief history*. *Therapeutic Recreation Journal*, 26(2), 5–13.
- Li, Y., Zhang, H., & Wang, J. (2021). Bibliometric analysis of physical therapy and rehabilitation research. *BMC Health Services Research*, 21, 1123. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-021-07064-9>
- Picton, C., Moxham, L., & Patterson, C. (2016). Therapeutic recreation for people with a mental illness is beneficial. *Australian Nursing & Midwifery Journal*, 23(10), 39.

Cited in: Temur, E. (2025). Conceptualization of Therapeutic Recreation and Emerging Themes: A Bibliometric Analysis. *Nortis Journal Of Sports Sciences*, Volume(1), 40 - 48

Small, H. (2019). Co-citation in the scientific literature: A new measure of the relationship between two documents. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science*, 24(4), 265–269.

Stumbo, N. J., & Peterson, C. A. (2020). *Therapeutic recreation program design: Principles and procedures*. Sagamore Publishing.

Sturm, B., Walter, P., & Rumpf, H. (2020). Bibliometric mapping of intervention research in recreational therapy. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, 1024. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.01024>

van Eck, N. J., & Waltman, L. (2010). Software survey: VOSviewer, a computer program for bibliometric mapping. *Scientometrics*, 84(2), 523–538. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-009-0146-3>

Zhang, Y., Chen, L., & Sun, H. (2022). Trends and developments in leisure and recreation studies: A bibliometric review. *Leisure Studies*, 41(7), 1240–1259. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02614367.2022.2041235>

Zupic, I., & Čater, T. (2015). Bibliometric methods in management and organization. *Organizational Research Methods*, 18(3), 429–472. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1094428114562629>